

Effective control of sheath rot (ShR) disease

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ShR, caused by *Sarocladium oryzae* (Saw) Gem., is a serious disease in the North Arcot District of India. We studied the efficacy of different fungicides for ShR control in a field trial using ADT35.

Table 1. Evaluation scale for ShR damage to rice in Tamil Nadu, India.

Sheath area affected	Grade
Less than 1%	1
1-5%	3
6-25%	5
26-50%	7
More than 50%	9

There were seven treatments in a randomized block design with four replications. Fungicides were sprayed 40 and 60 d after transplanting. Disease intensity was measured by selecting 10 hills at random, from which 1 tiller with maximum infection was taken for grading (Table 1).

Table 2. Efficacy of some fungicides for ShR control, Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment/ha	Disease intensity (mean)	Mean yield (t/ha)	% yield increase over control	Cost ^a of treatment/ha (\$)
Tridemorph (100 ml) + carbendazim (100 g)	0.87	4.6	37.4	11.55
Tridemorph (200 ml)	1.40	4.6	36.8	8.20
Tridemorph (100 ml) + mancozeb (500 g)	2.15	4.5	34.3	10.85
Carbendazim (100 g) + mancozeb (500 g)	2.40	4.3	28.9	14.30
Carbendazim (200 g)	2.97	4.3	27.6	15.00
Mancozeb (1000 g)	4.65	4.1	22.2	14.20
Control	6.80	3.4	—	—
CD (P = 0.05)	0.73	—	—	—

^aConverted at the rate of \$1 = Rs 11.44.

All treatments significantly reduced disease intensity and significantly increased the yield over the control (Table 2). Tridemorph at 100 ml + carbendazim at 100 g/ha or tridemorph at 200 ml/ha performed best at both application dates. □

Pest control and management INSECTS

Elaphropeza, a new pupal parasite of rice gall midge (GM) in India

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During a survey of GM *Orseolia oryzae* parasites in Orissa, we found a new pupal parasite. It was identified as *Elaphropeza* sp. (Diptera: Empididae) by Dr. K. G. V. Smith of the British Museum, London. The adult *Elaphropeza* is fragile, red, and 1.5 mm long. Its abdomen is 0.5 mm long, and wings are as long as the body. The parasite occurs infrequently in rice fields and parasitized less than 1% GM pupae in the field in Oct (wet season). In other months, it was not detected. The parasite maggot attacked the GM pupa externally. Pupation took place inside the gall. The maggots occasionally behaved as hyperparasites on pupae of *Platyaster oryzae*

(Cameron), a dominant egg-larval parasite of GM in Bhubaneswar. □

Population dynamics of the brown planthopper (BPH) in the Mekong Delta

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BPH is the most important rice pest in Vietnam, particularly in the Mekong Delta. BPH outbreaks occurred in 1969, 1971, 1973, and 1974 in almost all provinces in central and southern Vietnam.

Light trap collection data and field observations in Long An (1978-79) and Tien Giang (1977-78) provinces showed that BPH are active almost all year (see figure).

Cropping pattern determines seasonal BPH population in the Mekong Delta.

Rainfed and irrigated rice areas significantly differ in seasonal BPH populations

In Long An, a rainfed area, there are two annual crops grown: May-Sep and Oct-Feb. There are 10 to 11 BPH generations from May to Feb. No rice is grown between Feb and Apr.

There are about 25-30 d from 1 generation peak to the next. Two population peaks usually develop each year, one in each crop season. Peak population generally occurs at or after panicle initiation – Jul-Aug and Dec-Jan.

In Tien Giang, an irrigated area, there are three crop seasons with short-duration varieties: summer, May-Aug; autumn, Sep-Dec; and winter, Dec-Apr. There are 11-12 BPH generations/yr with 3 population peaks – Aug, Dec, and Mar.

In both areas, light-trap catches of BPH are largest 12-15 d after high nymph

populations in the field are observed.

Rainfall and humidity significantly affect BPH populations. Populations are low late in the dry season. Temperature in the Mekong Delta rarely falls below 22°C or exceeds 31°C, and therefore does not limit BPH.

Natural enemies reduced BPH population in fields where no insecticide was applied. Predators such as spiders, *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* and *Synharmonia octomaculata* were common. Egg parasites, mainly *Anagrus* sp., sometimes parasitized more than 90% of BPH eggs.

Rice varieties with the *bph 2* gene for resistance — IR36, IR38, IR2070, IR2071 — reduced the BPH population in the field, but IR8 and varieties with the *Bph 1* gene such as IR26, IR30, and IR1561-228-3-3 were msceptible to the local BPH population.

BPH populations have decreased since 1979 because of the intensive cultivation of IR36 and other resistant varieties.

Seasonal occurrence of BPH on rice fields in Mekong Delta, Vietnam. A = two rainfed crop areas of Long An (1978-79), and B = three irrigated crop areas of Tien Giang (1977-78).

Feeding activity of the green leafhopper (GLH) and tungro (RTV) infection

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We studied the relationship between feeding rate and number of feeding punctures by GLH and RTV infection on IR8, IR24, IR40, IR29, and IR22.

Two viruliferous GLH adults were caged in a honeydew collection chamber attached to the leaves of 20-d-old potted plants. Each variety was replicated 10 times, each chamber on a plant equaling 1 replication. The insects were allowed to feed for 22 h and the honeydew excreted by the insects was collected on filter paper treated with bromocresol green solution. The area of the honeydew spots on the paper was measured. Blue basic honeydew spots indicated phloem feeding, and were measured separately. The plants on which the hoppers fed were kept 20 d in the greenhouse for RTV symptom development and percent infection was computed.

To determine the number of feeding punctures made by GLH, 2 leaves on each

Table 1. Feeding punctures, honeydew excretion, and RTV infection, IRRI.^a

Variety	Feeding punctures (no.)	Total area (mm ²) of honeydew spots	Area (%) of basic honeydew spots	RTV infection (%)
IR8	82 c	188 b	49 b	76 b
IR24	125 a	179 b	52 b	71 b
IR40	110 ab	172 b	43 b	43 c
IR29	88 bc	179 b	10 c	14 d
IR22	45 d	228 a	100 a	99 a

^a Means in a column followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

of 10 plants/variety were enclosed in a parafilm sachet with 2 adult GLH females. Leaf portions fed upon by the insects were cut and dipped in 1% rhodamine solution for 15 min to stain the feeding punctures pink. The punctures were counted under a binocular microscope.

Although significant differences were observed on the total honeydew excreted, percent basic honeydew, RTV infection, and feeding punctures among the varieties tested (Table 1), there was no significant correlation between total honeydew and RTV infection and between total honeydew and feeding punctures (Table 2). However, a positive

Table 2. Correlation between RTV infection and GLH feeding activity, IRRI.

Feeding activity	Correlation coefficient ^a	
	RTV infection	
Feeding punctures	0.0062	ns
Total honeydew excreted	0.47	ns
% basic honeydew	0.92	**

^a Significance at the 0.05 level = 0.666; significance at the 0.01 level (**) = 0.798. ns = not significant.

correlation between basic honeydew and RTV infection indicated that phloem feeding is necessary for RTV infection.